

THE EFFECT OF SUSTAINABLE PROCUREMENT PRACTICES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF LOGISTICS COMPANIES IN KENYA: (A CASE OF BUZEKI LOGISTICS LTD.)

THOMAS TIRIMBA GETENGA

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Abstract: Understanding the variables that affect sustainable procurement and how they affect the operation of logistics companies is critically lacking. Purchasing is crucial for incorporating sustainable development concepts throughout all logistic companies' Therefore; this study was conducted to the effect of sustainable procurement practices on the performance of logistics companies in Kenya. (A case of Buzeki Logistics Ltd.) A descriptive research design was used in the study, and a stratified random selection technique with a target population of 75 respondents was targeted. According to the analysis, local buying practices, eco-friendly packaging, and reverse logistics had a positive and significant relationship with the performance of Buzeki Logistics Ltd, with a P-value of less than 0.05.

Keywords: Sustainability, Local Buying Practice, Eco-Friendly Packaging, Reverse Logistics, Performance of Logistics Companies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development, highlighted as the cornerstone for sustainable purchasing, is an important global goal for the future. The major objectives of sustainable procurement are to create equal opportunities, enhance social cohesion and individual well-being, and meet the diverse demands of every person in the present and future societies. Additionally, by creating advantages for the organization's culture, economics, and environmental sustainability, it helps enterprises to meet their needs for commodities, services, utilities, and construction work in a way that maximizes value for money over the long term.

According to Chogo and Kitheka (2019), logistics companies must develop complete procurement strategies that take ownership of social, ethical, and environmental procurement. This will offer more economical choices while reducing the environmental impact along the production chain. Masudin et al. (2018) assert that these methods would produce values that go beyond merely utilitarian and not only benefit the corporation purchasing them but also communicate the actual benefits to economies and society. These practices are frequently referred to as sustainable purchasing practices. Logistics businesses must frequently and quickly adapt to the current competitive environment to gain new competitive advantages. Purchasing is essential for achieving sustainable development. Therefore, these policies, procedures, and tactics must be expanded across all SC levels, despite any company limitations. This necessitates involving vendors at all levels in order to

add value during conversion. Sustainability guiding principles urge procurement to undertake evaluations that consider the triple bottom line's societal, environmental and economic components (Anane, Adoma & Awuah, 2019).

Global environmental and social sustainability challenges have grown in importance in recent years, putting more pressure on companies to alter their business practices, particularly in the supply chain, in order to lessen the negative effects of suppliers' actions on the environment. For the benefit of society, logistics companies must implement ethical and sustainable purchasing policies (Somjai & Jermstittiparsert, 2019).

Investors, staff members, and policymakers are placing more internal pressure on logistics firms, particularly those in developing nations, to enhance the social and environmental components of their supply chains (Muema & Achuora, 2020). The new environmental and social dimensions of the triple bottom line. This is because most businesses prioritize profit over all else and give long-term environmental issues little consideration.

According to Ayimba & Awuor, (2020) there are still gaps in the success factors for procurement-related operations. Despite the fact that the Kenyan government has implemented a number of institutional and legal regulations, such as NEEMA, to control commercial operations and guarantee environmental protection. All organizations in the nation are required to abide by the norms and regulations of the Act. Many private companies in Kenya seek to run more sustainably, and sustainable procurement seems to have a greater influence on organizational adoption. Naibei, (2020) claims that because doing so would result in higher expenses, Kenyan businesses are having trouble establishing a balance between the need for sustainable procurement and overall performance.

The management of an organization's procurement processes along the entire supply chain in accordance with the triple bottom line concept is known as sustainability in procurement. (Ayimba & Awuor, 2020). Sustainable procurement, commonly referred to as environmental or "green" purchasing, looks at the product's quality, contract, or service as well as its environmental impact. Regardless of size, all firms can benefit from using green purchasing methods. Green procurement tactics can be as simple as recycling office paper or purchasing renewable energy, or they can be more difficult, like enforcing environmental requirements on suppliers and contractors.

Logistic Companies in Kenya

Transportation is one of the most important aspects of every country's economy. It is, therefore, a crucial element of any company. The Act of physically connecting your business to the other stakeholders in your supply chain is known as this. Simply put, Mombasa clearing and forwarding companies ship physical goods to numerous other locations in Kenya and across Eastern Africa (Kivuva, 2018). Effective transport logistics connect a company to its suppliers and customers. Customers want to move goods quickly but affordably. Thus, getting in touch with Kenyan air freight companies is a smart idea. An airplane is, without a doubt, the fastest form of transportation. If not, permit customers' goods to be transported by maritime freight companies at a lesser cost. Customers can be sure that their operations will run smoothly when a reliable company handles all their transport logistics services in Kenya. It's crucial to cater to clients' speed. Customers, therefore, don't want late delivery, resulting in complaints (Monica, 2018).

It is frequently crucial to be safe when being carried. This is especially true today because terrorists and arsonists are ready to harm businesses (Wangai & Kariuki, 2020). Fortunately for consumers, air freight companies can provide armed security, especially for the most expensive commodities. Otherwise, heavy metal is utilized in building vehicles and containers to fend off even the most determined thief. When choosing the best means of transportation, customers should also consider the cost. Make sure customers don't spend excessive amounts of money, so you don't lose money or make any at all. Undoubtedly, faster orders cost more than slower ones. In order to offset the costs of transportation, customers should pay extra for items (Monica, 2018).

Buzeki Logistics Ltd

Buzeki Enterprises Limited, the business conglomerate with a global view and the flagship company of the Buzeki Group of Companies, is growing quickly. Having both a global and local focus, Buzeki Enterprises Limited is a centrally managed business owned by native Kenyan businesspeople. The Buzeki Group was founded in 1999 with the goal of providing a wide range of transport services in Kenya and the more significant East and Central African regions. Buzeki is a diverse corporate organization representing several industries and interests in those fields (Emukule, 2019).

Regional Transport Company in East Africa owned and registered locally is Buzeki Enterprises Limited. The rapid growth of the regional markets has raised the demand for high-quality transportation services to meet the needs of different industries, including manufacturing, distribution, and agricultural (Mbiti & Maina, 2018). Such needs would call for a business that, in addition to offering transportation services, would also encourage and guarantee professionalism, resulting in complete customer value and satisfaction while tending to transportation's urgent needs. The Buzeki Group's creators were aware of this fact and quickly rose to the situation by forming the Transport division of Buzeki Enterprises Limited in 2004.

The Buzeki Group has made a name for itself as a business known for professionalism in shipping operations, respecting safety standards, and having the ability to guarantee quality "as-scheduled" delivery. The dynamic business of Buzeki Enterprises Limited, which is dedicated to excellent customer service and safety, continually relies on maintaining a just and efficient fleet that can meet any number of client needs at any given time (Wangai & Kariuki, 2020).

Buzeki Enterprises Limited is currently one of the top companies in the logistics sector. It takes pleasure in providing its clients with unique, incredibly trustworthy, and high-quality transportation services. To ensure that our clients get the most for their money, Buzeki Enterprises highly emphasizes efficiency and exceptional service. Buzeki Enterprises constantly ensures that all of its fleets are kept current and continue to abide by transport licensing requirements. (Mbiti & Maina, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Understanding the variables that affect sustainable procurement and how they affect the operation of logistics companies is critically lacking. Businesses do not have a clear plan for regular chores, methodologies, or procedures to include sustainability in the procurement process, claims Mburu, (2017). Purchasing is crucial for incorporating sustainable development concepts throughout the logistic companies' American activities, claims a paper by Masudin et al., (2018). Despite the fact that many logistics companies recognize the significance of sustainability, it is still challenging to put an effective plan into action in order to build a successful business. Chogo and Kitheka, (2019). One such area is procurement, which helps to promote sustainability by reducing resource consumption as well as the undesirable effects of production, distribution, and product disposal after their useful lives, all of which have never been thoroughly studied. Despite a study by Odero and Ayub, (2017) showing uncertainty that sustainable procurement procedures could produce economic benefits, Masudin et al., (2018) suggested that the SP could lead to a higher financial commitment, diminishing economic gains. According to Anane, Adoma, and Awuah's (2019) research, SP practices are now acknowledged as crucial tools businesses in the UK can utilize to boost their profitability.

Karaman, Kilic and Uyar's , (2020) found that the Middle Eastern countries, in particular, had not conducted a thorough investigation into the effect of SP practices on financial performance. Ismail, et al., (2019) looked at the type of research done from 2014 to 2018. Locally, Muema & Achuora's (2020) research findings revealed that working with clients to promote environmental responsibility is the most effective method to increase financial performance. In contrast, Ayimba & Awuor, (2020) found no conclusive connections between green purchasing and asset or sales returns, which ultimately impact a business's ability to succeed financially.

There has not been much research on what makes sustainable purchasing possible in Kenyan logistics. Because there was only a tenuous link between the performance of the supply chain and sustainable procurement methods, this study was important to ascertain why sustainable procurement was still not fully recognized in logistics business practices. The research was driven by this knowledge gap and aimed to explain sustainability-related terms and figure out why it was challenging for transport and logistics companies in Kenya to include sustainability in their procurement practices.

The objective of the Study

- a) To assess the effects of local buying practices on the performance of logistics companies in Kenya.
- b) To determine the effects of eco-friendly packaging on the performance of logistics companies in Kenya.
- c) To find out how reverse logistics on the performance of logistics companies in Kenya.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Local Buying Practice and Performance of Logistics Companies

According to Schoolman (2020), purchasing locally entails incorporating neighboring purchases into a company's core operations. Vukovic, (2019) emphasized that the business should only select suppliers who can be conveniently found in the neighborhood, even though the precise proximity requirements may vary. Locally produced items positively impact the environment since their carbon footprints are less, they require fewer preservatives to extend their shelf lives, and their packaging is shoddier. Individual players, technologies, and local traditions comprise the micro-level (niche level).

According to Wickert, Vaccaro, and Cornelissen, (2017) in order to make local purchasing more sustainable, initiatives involving the key players, the community, and customers should all be considered. These companies typically gain from their favorable customer and community perceptions. Organizational executives, particularly those who work from home, are increasingly required to ensure that their businesses behave as "good corporate citizens." Lead times that are shorter and more incredible supplier sourcing skills. According to Liyanage & Wijesundara, (2020) are all reasons why local purchasing increases organizational performance. This is because businesses are located in actual locations, and the significant community supporting an organization's operational activities can have a sense of belonging due to the regional buying strategy.

The environmental benefits of sustainable purchasing frequently impact how money is used in the industries they operate. The only way to incorporate environmental considerations into the procurement process and accomplish green procurement is to look at things over their complete life cycle, from purchase through disposal. Local raw material acquisitions increase company productivity by ensuring that products are recyclable, energy-efficient, biodegradable, and devoid of ozone-depleting chemicals (Wickert, Vaccaro & Cornelissen, 2017).

Eco-Friendly Packaging and Performance of Logistics Companies

In addition to protecting goods and enabling effective logistics, the packaging is essential for the essential marketing role of the supply chain. Eight frameworks for sustainable packaging have been outlined by Ramadan et al., (2020). Throughout its life cycle, sustainable packaging must be made from decent materials, use recycled resources, follow best practices for clean production, be helpful, secure, and healthy for people and groups, and products using these criteria. Meets market demands for cost and efficiency.

However, Moustaf, et al., (2019) assert that three groups can be broadly grouped when it comes to eco-friendly packaging: consumers, governments, and scientists. Therefore, from that vantage point, ecologically friendly packaging may be assessed. Government ecological efficiency is linked to legal obligations like the proper way to recycle or dispose of hazardous materials. A life cycle evaluation perspective is frequently used in scientific green to examine an item's effects throughout its life cycle. The consumer category discusses consumer perceptions of environmental friendliness and reactions to packaging.

According to Safaei, (2020) the factors that influence consumers' propensity to buy ecologically packaged goods, consumers are apparently growing more willing to adjust how they use packaging while taking the factors that influence ecologically packaged products into account. Key discriminating factors included the internal control environment, perceived pollution, attitudes toward littering, and a living environment that emphasized the environment. Effective eco-friendly communication requires a variety of preconditions, according to Fernandes and Madhuranthakam (2021). When independent regulating bodies issue certificates, they seem to have more credibility. For instance, Safaei, (2020) started the 4Rs program to boost the use of renewable resources in manufacturing and raise the amount of recycled content in packaging.

Reverse Logistics and Performance of Logistics Companies

In recent decades, the significance of a product's environmental impact has increased (Prajapati, Kant & Shankar, 2019). As governments increase their environmental regulations and consumers grow more ecologically aware, the sector needs to reduce the environmental impact of its products. Businesses have attempted to boost their environmental efficiency by participating in the supply chain. Businesses are now thinking about managing the environment through responsible waste disposal and using reverse logistics as a result of this fact. As a result, disposal plans and environmental laws for a corporation sometimes incorporate RL operations.

Waste management, material recycling, component restoration, and rehabilitation through reprocessing are the main issues in reverse logistics. Reverse logistics encompasses more than just packaging recycling and container reuse. Tracking logistical returns, properly disposing of waste, and recycling waste is also included in reverse logistics (Sirisawat & Kiatcharoenpol, 2018). Reverse logistics as a whole may be more important than modifying packaging to use less resources or to cut down on energy and pollution from transportation. Reverse logistics processing, hazardous material recall, disposal plans, asset recovery, and damage control are all included in the management of returned goods. According to Julianelli, et al., (2020), supply chain leadership is undergoing an exciting and crucial transformation as a result of the realization of the strategic importance of inverse logistics activities in enterprises. Reverse logistics transactions can be utilized for a variety of purposes, including "green logistics" as well as boosting product yields, maintaining, and remodeling. Among these are "initiatives for reducing the supply chain's environmental impact." Reverse logistics procedures can increase the value of a consumer while reducing the risk they experience when purchasing a product (Sathish & Jayaprakash, 2017).

A comprehensive logistics plan that promotes effectiveness, efficiency, and differentiation may include reverse logistics as a key component. Through reverse logistics, businesses are getting better at recovering value from their products (Sirisawat & Kiatcharoenpol, 2018). A strong correlation between the development of reverse logistics competencies and reductions in operating costs has been observed in a prior study. Businesses can save money and increase their focus on customer happiness and other service-related issues by cooperating to use resources more wisely than their competitors; they can raise the bar for sustainable development and business success (Sathish & Jayaprakash, 2017).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework

3. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design was used in the study, which took a quantitative approach—understanding the where, what, and how of a phenomenon involves descriptive investigation. The fact that no data was gathered for this study and no variables were altered served as the foundation for it. The plan that guides the study participants' selection, the data gathering, and the analysis and interpretation of that data are known as research designs (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019). The target population was workers from the administration/stores, finance, logistics, and procurement/supply departments.

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According to Buzeki Logistics Ltd.'s human resource database 2022, 280 employees were working in the administration/stores, finance, and logistics divisions. Using a stratified random selection technique, the researcher selected a 20% sample from the target mentioned above. Twenty percent is accepted as a sufficient number because, according to Bloomfield & Fisher, (2019) a representative must represent at least 20 percent of the target demographic. The table below demonstrates how this could be done:

Table 1: Sample Size

Departments	Staff	Sample %	Sample size
Center management department	10	20%	2
Administration/Stores	95	20%	19
Logistics	120	20%	24
Finance department	150	20%	30
Total	280	20%	75

Sources: (Buzeki Logistics Ltd human resource database 2022)

SPSS version 20.0 programming was used to analyze the data. In regard to the study's specific goals, the results were presented as mean and standard deviation tables. Through the use of correlation analysis, the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent components was examined. Regression analysis was employed, however, to estimate the strength of the correlation between the variables. The used regression model looked like this;

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3$$

Where:

Y = Performance of Logistics Companies

β_0 = Constant Term

β_1 = Beta coefficients

X1= Local Buying Practice

X2= Eco-Friendly Packaging

X3= Reverse Logistics

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

There were 75 participants in the study, but only 62 completed the survey, translating to an 82.6 percent response rate. According to Bloomfield & Fisher, (2019) a response rate of 51% is sufficient for analysis and reporting. In addition, the optimum response rate is at least 69%. This response rate was therefore sufficient for analysis and reporting, allowing study findings to be deduced.

Local Buying Practice and Performance of Logistics Companies

The questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive statistics to analyze, particularly an analysis of questions related to this section using mean scores and standard deviations to evaluate the local buying practice effects performance of logistics companies. According to the questionnaire, respondents were asked if they strongly disagreed or strongly agreed with several statements. The results and the mean and standard deviation are shown in the table below.

Table 2: Local buying practice statement

Descriptive Statistics		
Local buying practice statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Companies work with suppliers who are conveniently located in the area.	3.4194	1.57385
Companies should be encouraged to work with suppliers who are conveniently located in the area.	3.6452	1.40370

The business should be encouraged to work with suppliers who are conveniently located in the area.	3.5484	1.46743
Local purchasing reduces the need for conservative measures that increase shelf life and reduce packing.	3.1129	1.57963
Local buying improves organizational performance through shorter lead times and improved supplier-purchase comprehension.	3.5323	1.59628

The study sought to determine whether local buying practices affect logistics companies' performance. Based on the findings from table 4.2, it shows that companies should be encouraged to work with conveniently located suppliers in the area. This finding was in line with Wickert, Vaccaro, and Cornelissen, (2017). They argued that in order to make local purchasing more sustainable, initiatives involving the key players' customers should be put in place. These businesses generally benefit from their excellent reputations with customers and the community. Organizational executives, particularly those who work from home, are increasingly required to ensure that their businesses behave as "good corporate citizens."

Eco-Friendly Packaging and Performance of Logistics Companies

The second objective was determining how eco-friendly packaging affects logistics companies' performance. The results mean and standard deviations are displayed in the table below.

Table 3: Eco-friendly packaging statement

Descriptive Statistics		
Eco-friendly packaging statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Reduce the company's carbon footprint to boost its profitability.	3.5194	1.49829
The company's customers can tell that the business is sincere about its dedication to sustainability, thanks to eco-friendly packaging.	3.6100	1.48602
Environmentally friendly packaging helps a logistics company perform better.	3.2713	1.63781
Eco-friendly packaging reduces the quantity of packaging material necessary to convey goods; as a result, it is more cost-effective for businesses and their clients.	3.5294	1.71479
Eco-friendly encourages customers to be more conscientious of the garbage they make and diverts waste from landfills.	3.6978	1.72407

This demonstrated that environmentally friendly packaging was having a stronger impact on logistics companies' performance, indicating that Buzeki Logistics Ltd had embraced the usage of environmentally friendly packaging in an effort to improve their performance. The findings conform to Safaei, (2020) that recommended that consumers' propensity to buy ecologically packaged goods, consumers are apparently growing more willing to make adjustments to the way they use packaging while taking the factors that influence ecologically packaged products into account.

Reverse Logistics and Performance of Logistics Companies

The last objective to study was to assess reverse logistics and the performance of logistics companies. The results, including the mean and standard deviation, are shown in the table below.

Table 4: Reverse logistics statement

Descriptive Statistics		
Reverse Logistics Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Effective customer retention is a very beneficial feature of reverse logistics.	3.0323	1.47067
The use of recycled or renewable resources is maximized via reverse logistics.	3.4355	1.59529
Reverse logistics procedures that are simplified make it possible to cut back on a variety of costs related to fake returns.	3.6935	1.27509
Any effective supply chain that has been optimized now includes reverse logistics as a critical element.	3.4355	1.48899
Reverse logistics focuses primarily on waste management and material recycling, enhancing logistics companies' performance.	3.1613	1.53851

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According to the questionnaire, respondents were asked if they strongly disagreed or strongly agreed with a number of statements to establish how reverse logistics and performance of logistics companies. This shows that Buzeki Logistics Ltd's reverse logistics procedures were simplified and made it possible to cut back on a variety of costs related to fake returns. The findings conform to Sirisawat & Kiatcharoenpol, (2018) that through reverse logistics, businesses are getting better at recovering value from their products.

Inferential Statistics;

This quantitatively demonstrated the relationship between logistics companies' performance and the effects of sustainable buying methods.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.951a	.914	.891	.41498

In terms of the performance of logistics companies, the model explains 0.914 of the variations (Adjusted R Square= 0.891). It is obvious that there are more factors besides the three suggested in this model that may be used to analyze the performance of Buzeki Logistics Ltd. However, Bramsen & Poder, (2018) noted that even a lower value of R square (0.10-0.20) is acceptable in social science research; therefore, this is still a good model. This suggests that the local procurement practices, eco-friendly packaging, and reverse logistics, which were found, account for 91.4 percent of the relationship. Other factors not examined in this study's analysis of the impact of sustainable procurement practices on the performance of logistics companies account for the remaining 8.6 percent.

ANOVA table

Table 6: ANOVA table

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	94.343	3	31.448	182.613	.000b
	Residual	9.988	58	.172		
	Total	104.332	61			

The ANOVA test is performed to ascertain whether the model is significant in predicting logistics companies' performance. The ANOVA test, which had a significance level of 0.05, showed that the independent variables local buying practices, eco-friendly packaging, and reverse logistics were significant in predicting the performance of logistics companies, with a significance value of 0.000, or less than 0.05 ($p=0.000 < 0.05$). As a result, the dependent variable (performance of logistics companies) and the independent factors have a substantial association (local buying practice, eco-friendly packaging, and reverse logistics).

Coefficient of Regression

Table 7: Coefficient of Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.031	.336		-6.048	.000
Local Buying Practice	.496	.214	.327	2.321	.024
Eco-Friendly Packaging	.756	.192	.561	3.943	.000
Reverse Logistics	.316	.103	.140	3.068	.003

a. Performance of logistics companies

Final Optimal model; $Y = 2.031 + 0.496 x_1 + 0.756x_2 + .316 x_3$

$\beta_1 = 0.496$ local buying practices have a positive significance, thus affecting logistics companies' performance, with a P-value of 0.024, which is statistically significant as a measure of performance of Buzeki Logistics Ltd.

$\beta_2 = 0.756$ eco-friendly packaging has a positive significance, thus affecting the performance of logistics companies, and with a P-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant as a measure of performance of Buzeki Logistics Ltd.

$\beta_3 = 0.316$ A positive and significant relation between reverse logistics and the performance of logistics companies, and a P-value of 0.003, greater than $\alpha = 0.05$.

These results indicate that the model depicted a positive and significant relationship between the effects of sustainable procurement practices on the performance of logistics companies.

5. SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

The study indicated that Buzeki Logistics Ltd. was working with conveniently located suppliers in the area. Additionally, local purchasing practices reduced the demand for conservatives, increasing shelf life and reducing packing. Therefore, it demonstrates the importance of businesses developing their relationships with local suppliers. It was obvious that eco-friendly packaging was taking care of garbage by diverting it away from landfills because it also reduced firms' carbon footprint and increased their profitability. As a result, it demonstrates that organizations need to be encouraged to adopt eco-friendly packaging because it reduces the amount of packing. Reverse logistics has become crucial to any effective, efficient supply chain.

6. RECOMMENDATION OF THE STUDY

Improving environmental, social, and financial efficiency across the entire procurement cycle will help address sustainable procurement concerns. To act in the interests of stakeholders and society at large, the study advises Buzeki Logistics Ltd. to undergo a significant transformation in its local purchasing practices. Based on the critical role that eco-friendly packaging plays in organizational success, Buzeki Logistics Ltd. must begin to see sustainable procurement as a strategic goal. Future plans for the company will be impacted, and the environment, business climate, and culture will all benefit. The study recommends that Buzeki Logistics Ltd. concentrate on the management of waste, recovery of material, as well as restoration of the component. This results from the favorable correlations between the growth of inverse logistics skills and decreases in organizational and operational costs. Reverse logistics will therefore have a significant impact on Buzeki Logistics Ltd's performance.

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